

Review of HRM Practices in Banks from Developing Countries

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this review was to study the impact of HRM practices in banks. Banking being a service sector, a committed and productive team plays an important role in the growth of the organization. The HR (Human Resource) department's job is to acquire and train capable manpower and place them in the right job at the right time. On the other hand job, satisfaction on the employee's end is one of the most important variables for the implementation of strategic HRM policies to stay relevant. This review has established that the HRM practices in the banks globally have a few things in common regarding job satisfaction among the employees and they are: training, performance appraisal, compensation, reward, employee motivation, and engagement, etc. are the most important variables to boost the organization's performance.

Keywords: HRM practices, Bank, Developing countries

INTRODUCTION

In the current digital era, banks have moved from traditional paper-based ways of functioning to the sophisticated technology that needs skilled manpower to enhance the efficiency of the organization. Therefore the HR department has a multifaceted role of selecting, recruiting, training, developing the right skill mix of staff by acquainting them with the organizations goals and realizing the goals to stay in the competitive zone (Schuler and Jackson, 1987)

Banking being a service sector, a committed and productive team plays an important role in the growth of the organization. The HR (Human Resource) department's job is to acquire and train capable manpower and place them in the right job at the right time (Mehta, 2016). On the other hand job, satisfaction on the employee's end is one of the most important variables for the implementation of strategic HRM policies to stay relevant (Ijigu, 2015).

HRM practices have a major influence on the financial performance of the banks (Masood et al., 2010). The escalating global competition in the banking industry calls for HR policies tailored to the needs of the organization and its employees and therefore this review plans to study the various HRM practices in the banking sector to enhance the progression of any organization and retain its skilled employees.

LITERATURE REVIEW

This review has taken examples from different countries around the globe to review the HRM practices that are carried out in their banking sectors and they are as follows:

Bangladesh

A survey was done by Majumder (2012), on the HRM practices in a private bank in Bangladesh. The sample was 100 employees, out of which responses from 88 employees were considered valid and the statistical analysis revealed the following results: most of the bank employees were dissatisfied with the compensation package, motivation, reward, training, development, management styles, responsibilities, and job conditions. The study also reflected on the need to employ HR consultants and researchers to work in tandem to develop new policies for improving the efficiency of the HR practices in the bank. They had concerns regarding a few issues, for example: that despite having adequate technology the training of employees was rather slow and inefficient and they wanted better functioning between the employees and the management.

India

In India, a survey was conducted by Vikramjeet and Sayeeduzzafar (2014) on the employees of HDFC bank regarding their level of job satisfaction. The results revealed that teamwork, compensation, and training had a significant positive impact on job satisfaction and most of the employees were satisfied with these features of job satisfaction. Employee

participation had a negative but significant impact on job satisfaction. Their recommendation was to improve employee participation at the senior and middle-order rank of employees.

China

Employee-centric organizations like banks that have a service-oriented agenda, must encourage employee participation which is very essential for the growth of the company (Ali et al., 2016). A survey done in a Chinese bank elicited that the good employee relation environment is an important mediator between planned HRM and the performance of the organization (Ali et al., 2016).

Pakistan

A study in Pakistan (Masood et al., 2010), on thirty-eight scheduled banks, found that selection, compensation, training, participation by employees are important variables that impact the financial performance of the banks.

Ethiopia

Ijigu (2015) has drawn attention to the situation in Ethiopian banks and their HRM practices. Training, development, performance appraisal, and compensation are highly correlated to job satisfaction in the banking sector. Selection and recruitment have a moderate but positive correlation to job satisfaction. The study suggested that constant evaluation of the HRM practices and two-way communications can help to boost employee's job satisfaction and loyalty and reduce absentee issues.

Pakistan

Employee motivation is an important mediating variable in post-HRM practices and organizational performance in a survey done on Islamic banks in Pakistan. Training and development, intrinsic and extrinsic rewards, career development, employee motivation, and performance and evaluation system were highly correlated to performance in Islamic Banks (Dar et al, 2014).

Lebanon

Zaraket and Halawi (2017) selected five mediating variables to assess the HRM practices of Lebanese banks and they are: job satisfaction, employee engagement, employee motivation, HR flexibility, and organizational citizen's behaviour. The results depict a significant correlation between HRM practices and employee retention but not attrition. There is a positive correlation between organizational citizen's behaviour and employee performance; job satisfaction and employee attrition; employee engagement and organizational performance; a negative correlation between employee engagement and attrition i.e. employees who are effectively engaged stay longer with the organization; motivated employees help to boost the organization's performance; HR flexibility improves employee retention and their performance; job satisfaction is positively related to good HRM policies, etc.

This study endorses that employee engagement helps to retain employees and their suggestions should be welcome for policy and procedural decisions. They must be recognized for their work via rewards compensation and there must be a benchmark they can attain which recognizes their quality of work (Zaraket and Halawi, 2017).

Features of the practices

- The HR department has to help the employees map their career growth and individual development within the space of their jobs and take on other roles.
- HR should provide adequate training to the employees and then evaluate their progress development and job satisfaction.
- The work culture of public sector banks differs from private sector banks as the former concentrates on socio-economic responsibility and the latter on profit. HR departments of public banks can make more efforts towards helping their employees by having precise selection and recruitment practices tailored to their needs of the employees so that they can achieve maximum potential and improve their job satisfaction levels.
- The HR department can be more generous with a reward, benefits system, and compensation package based on the employee's performance.
- There should be good co-ordination and co-operation between the employees and the management as it keeps the employees motivated and enhances their retention.
- The organizations must carry out research especially on the evaluation of HRM practices in the banks to improve employee and management relations.
- The Appraisal system of the bank must be in sync with the goals and objectives of the bank. Besides, the training programs conducted in public sector banks should be upgraded with the current scenarios and the consumer's varying needs.
- Promotions in the public sector banks are on a hierarchical basis in contrast to the private sector where promotions are more work based.

(Zaraket and Halawi, 2017; Ijigu, 2015; Majumder, 2012; Mehta, 2016; Mellacheruvu and Krishnamacharyulu, 2008; Trivedi, 2008)

CONCLUSION

This review has established that the HRM practices in the banks globally have a few things in common regarding job satisfaction among the employees and they are: training, performance appraisal, compensation, reward, employee motivation, and engagement are the most important variables to boost the organization's performance.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Ali, M., Xiao, S.L., and Wei, Y. (2016). The mediating role of the employee relations climate in the relationship between strategic HRM and organizational performance in Chinese banks. *Journal of Innovation & Knowledge*, 3(3). 115-122.
- [2]. Dar, A.T., Bashir, M., Ghazanfar, F., and Abrar, M. (2014). Mediating Role of Employee Motivation in Relationship to Post-Selection HRM Practices and Organizational Performance. *International Review of Management and Marketing*, 4(3), 224-238
- [3]. Ijigu, A.W., (2015). The Effect of Selected Human Resource Management Practices on Employees' Job Satisfaction in Ethiopian Public Banks. *Emerging Markets Journal*, 5(1).
- [4]. Majumder, M.T.H. (2012). Human Resource Management Practices and Employees' Satisfaction Towards Private Banking Sector in Bangladesh. *International Review of Management and Marketing*, 2(1), 52-58.
- [5]. Masood, Q., Akbar, A., Khan, M.A., Sheikh, R.A., Hijaz, S.T. (2010). Do human resource management practices have an impact on financial performance of banks? *African Journal of Business Management*, 4(7), 1281-1288.
- [6]. Mehta, E. (2016). Literature Review on HR Practice in Banking Sector. *International Research Journal of Engineering, IT & Scientific Research (IRJEIS)*, 2(7), 90-97.
- [7]. Mellacheruvu, S and Krishnamacharyulu, C.S.G. (2008). Challenges of Human Resource Management in Public Sector Banks. *JIMS*, 8 M, 42-45.
- [8]. Schuler, R.S. and Jackson, S.E. (1987). Linking competitive strategies with human resource management practices, *Academy of Management Executive*, 1(3), 207-19.
- [9]. Trivedi, V. (2008). HR Perspectives in Indian Banking System. *The Indian Journal of Commerce*, 61(1), 68-7.
- [10]. Vikramjeet and Sayeeduzzafar. (2014). A Study of HRM Practices and its Impact on Employees job Satisfaction in Private Sector Banks: A Case Study of HDFC Bank. *International Journal of Advance Research in Computer Science and Management Studies*, 2(1).
- [11]. Zaraket, W.S., and Halawi, A. (2017). The effects of HRM practices on organisational performance in Lebanese banks. *J. Global Business Advancement*, 10(1), 62-88.